

Multiple Celebrity Endorsement And Consumer Purchase Intention Of Public University Students

Professor Kennedy Ntabo Otiso

Associate Professor of Marketing,
School of Business, Koitaleel Samoei University College, Kenya

ABSTRACT

The present study examined the effect of multiple celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intention of public university students. All the 57,715 students of the public universities in Western Kenya were targeted, they include: Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology with a student population of 25,000, Kibabii University with a student population of 11,715, and lastly Maseno University with a population size of 21,000. The study used disproportionate stratified simple random sampling to sample 397 students of the three picked public Universities in Western Kenya, purposive sampling was utilized to sample three Ariel merchandisers promoting Ariel detergent in the three major towns in Western Kenya where the universities are located (Kakamega county, Bungoma county and Kisumu county). Data was then gathered through structured questionnaires and interview schedules. Pilot study and was then done to ascertain the study tools reliability as well as validity. Content of the tool was affirmed to be relevant to the study, and construct validity was tested using factor analysis. Reliability was tested using Cronbach (Alpha – α) which found out that the tool was valid and reliable. Both descriptive (means, standard deviations and frequency distribution) and inferential analysis (Pearson correlation and linear regression models) were utilized. The study also employed the use of multiple linear regression to determine the strength of the four variables in influencing consumer purchase intention of public university students in Western Kenya. The investigation uncovered that Multiple Celebrity Endorsement possessed a statistically significant positive influence on the consumer purchase intention of public university students Western, Kenya $\beta = 0.0.661$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$. The study concluded that the multiple celebrity endorsement had significantly strong positive causal influence on the customer purchase intentions had influence on consumer purchase intentions of public university students in Western Kenya. The study recommends that brands and marketers to have proper consideration of celebrity attributes while selecting celebrity endorsers. Marketers should consider other salient factors involved when using celebrity endorsement as a promotion tool. Future studies should consider exploring these other elements not covered that significantly influences consumer purchase intentions.

Keywords: Celebrity, Multiple Celebrity, Endorsement, Consumer, Purchase Intentions

INTRODUCTION

According to Nganga (2013), just a small percentage of consumers are not swayed by celebrity endorsement while buying an item. Likewise, loyalty of customer is impacted by previous product experience, therefore celebrity endorsement is quite successful in raising sales volume (Onyancha, 2016). The findings additionally found that customers decide to buy a product when it has similar traits like those of the products endorsed by the celebrity (Njoroge, 2013). Akinyi (2017) found that different celebrity attributes positively correlates with middle class consumers intention of purchase. This shows the impact of celebrities on purchasing behavior. According to the study, low-income individuals seldom buy celebrity-endorsed items, hence celebrity endorsements as a marketing approach are ineffective with them. Njuguna and Otieno (2015) in their research of celebrity endorsement and brand recall behavior among youth concluded that celebrity endorsement and more importantly the attractiveness

of the celebrity had an influence on the brand recall behavior among the youth in Nairobi. Now it is clear that research has been done on this topic. However, most of it has been based internationally and if locally then focused on the Nairobi locality or a specific product brand. Its agreeable to say that celebrity endorsement effectiveness is influenced by various celebrity traits which in turn influence the actual buying intention. The current study will examine the impact of celebrity endorsement on purchase intention among public university students in Western Kenya with object of study being Ariel detergent.

Statement of the Problem

Globally recognized brands such as Gucci, Nike, Adidas, and Chanel have increasingly allocated significant portions of their marketing budgets toward celebrity endorsement deals (Arora & Sahu, 2013). In Kenya, this trend is also gaining momentum, with numerous local celebrities being engaged to promote

various products. For example, Celina endorses Harpic toilet cleaner, Terryanne Chebet is associated with Molfix diapers, and both Jeff Koinange and Yvonne Okwara Matole promote Standard Chartered Bank. Additionally, in June 2020, the international alcohol brand Glenfiddich launched a refreshed bottle design in Kenya, endorsed by renowned Kenyan chef Mulunda Kombo. These endorsements span diverse product categories with varying consumer involvement levels, all leveraging celebrity influence to gain a competitive edge. However, despite these efforts, many companies in Kenya still continue to diversify their advertising strategies beyond celebrity endorsements. This suggests that the effectiveness of celebrity marketing may still be in question within the Kenyan context. With the growing influence of social media and increasingly vocal consumers who actively share their brand preferences, strategic advertising has become more crucial than ever. University students represent a key demographic— young adults entering an independent phase of life— who significantly influence each other's purchasing decisions (Zhao, Zhang, Liu, Zhang, Bao & Ren, 2020). Understanding and targeting this market segment could provide a substantial advantage to companies. For instance, Procter & Gamble East Africa (PGEA) has used local celebrity Mercy Masika to promote Ariel detergent, positioning it as superior in removing stains in one wash (Nzomo, 2013).

Despite this, PGEA has also adopted alternative advertising methods, such as the "One Wash" campaign, indicating a pursuit of more effective promotional strategies. In an era characterized by intense brand competition and the constant pursuit of market share, deeper insight is needed. Specifically, there is a need to understand which consumer segments are most influenced by celebrity endorsements, how endorsers are selected, and which attributes of these endorsers most impact consumer behavior. This study, therefore, aimed to explore the elements of celebrity endorsement that, if optimized, could enhance consumer purchase intentions. Notably, there is a lack of documented research examining the effectiveness of celebrity endorsements and their influence on purchasing decisions in Western Kenya. Thus, this study focused on assessing how various dimensions of celebrity endorsements affect the purchasing intentions of public university students in Western Kenya, using Ariel detergent as the case product.

Significance of the Study

Findings of the study will help marketers, brand managers in Kenya to decipher on the kind of celebrities that are worthwhile to promote their brand and improve consumer purchase intentions, and if at all to use celebrity endorsements. Findings will assist in policy making for advertisement, particularly for

The Competition Authority of Kenya, as well as other countries especially on execution when using celebrity endorsement for marketing communication.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

Mwikya (2013) states that a theory is an array of concepts presented systematically to explain a particular phenomenon. The proposed study will be mainly anchored on dual entertainment theory and supported by sources attractiveness model as presented by McGuire (1985), sources credibility model to explain the variables.

Sources Attractiveness Model

This social psychology model was proposed by McCracken (1989). It gives 4 categories of; familiarity, likeability, similarity, and attractiveness. It stipulates that a product's breakthrough is determined by its familiarity to the customers' awareness, acceptance, sameness, and attractiveness to the celebrity in the advertisement. The model describes acceptance message in twofold: Identification then Conditioning. Identification refers to when consumers begin to identify with the celebrity and as a result accepts its attributes and endorsements. Conditioning is about the attractiveness of the celebrity giving over their traits to the brand through mutual interactions. Kelman (1961) asserts that celebrity effort to market the product influences positively consumer behavior through identification process since buyers begin to relate with the product even more. The more consumers like the brand ambassadors the more the acceptance of endorsement message. Many organizations use celebrities because of their fame and preference by buyers. Consumers anticipate marketing adverts with high level of attraction toward the brand ambassador (Baker and Churchill, 1977). What consumers see attracts them to the product and brand (Clow, James, Kranenburg & Berry, 2006). Organizations that engage physically attractive celebrities as ambassadors for their products enjoy more brand recall (Singer, 1983). The reason for creating a good brand image is always to attract consumers (Milosavljevic and Cerf, 2008) and is famous among several marketing scholars.

It's important to note that people watch adverts for different reasons giving more attention to watching elements they like and ignoring those they don't like via selective attention. It is crucial to highlight, however, that physical beauty is a given for attraction (Milosavljevic and Cerf, 2008). Marketers go for beauty because of status and appeal (Singer, 1983). Contemporary advertisement must showcase physical beauty for them to be acceptable to the consumers. This subject has attracted diverse opinions from different scholars. According to McGuire (1985) this model remains a compulsory strategy for marketers.

However, Goldsmith et al. (2000) states that this concept has no influence to the credibility of organization. Physical attractiveness in its Self even with the many gains it potents, has no ultimate authority in influencing buying intentions. This contrast presents a gap for this study and the model discussed will be employed to anchor the variable on attractiveness of brand ambassadors and its influence on the buyer intentions.

Empirical Review

Multiple Endorsement and Consumer Purchase Intention

Celebrities’ can endorse either one product or multiple product lines according to the term of agreement with their producer. Indeed, its common place to find a case where a brand ambassador has more than one product to endorse (Nam-Hyun Um 2008). This last approach is known as multiple ambassador brand advocacy (Hsu and McDonald, 2002). This approach is twofold: an endorsement where two or even more and endorser endorses a brand together or an endorsement in which different brand ambassadors endorse a product brand through many adverts over time (Nam-Hyun Um, 2008). Hsu and McDonald (2002), in a study on multiple endorsements for consumer behaviour found that brand ambassadors complement one another even with their diversities in a multiple endorsement strategy. This ensures that the product or brand promoted acquires a wider view of transferred meanings. However, even in the place of their similarities, the similarities work as emphasis.

Reebok (2005) launched its embarked on a global multifaceted campaign dubbed (I am what I am). It advocated for youngsters in celebrating their icons such as the singers and sports persons. The result of this initiative has been leveraged by several firms that have engaged these icons on the promotional platforms. Some managers however believe that an icon would influence more sales through brand image than any other means. They are seen to have very strong personalities that easily change perceptions of people (Erdogan and Baker, 2000). However, it’s important to consider this strategy with caution and so mangers who engage in this should be able to balance the mix of preferences and diverse personalities of the celebrities (Erdogan and Baker, 2000). Friedman and Friedman (1977) stated that customers’ preferences were enhanced when there is brand endorsement by a celebrity. Schiffman (1997) stipulated that when one brand ambassador endorses one product, consumers were likely to be attracted it to it than many of them.

Previous studies on the subject of brand endorsements including Mowen and Brwon (1981) and Mowen, Brown and Schulman (1979) reveal that using many brand ambassadors may be confused to

decide on the product based on mixed feeling about the celebrities. This could be because of the fact that there is limited distinctiveness and divergent interests may arise. Additionally, this may reduce the impact of the brand ambassador on the good. (Tripp and Jensen 1994) as well as the quantity of goods a brand ambassador support negatively affects customer perceptions of the brand. McCracken (1989) says that meanings are carried on through ambassadors from one advert to another, plus this affects those assigned meanings. When a brand ambassador anchors many products, the endorsement influence loses its weight because since consumer preferences will be affected.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

As per Mugenda and Mugenda (2006), descriptive research design is employed to get data on the prevailing status of a phenomenon in comparison with prevailing conditions. The researcher will use a descriptive research design. This investigation utilized descriptive research design because it plans to collect quantitative data that would explain the traits of celebrity endorsement and purchase intention among Kenyan consumers. The descriptive survey was picked since it is ideal in collecting data in social research that is concerned with the description of the state of the variables and detailed description of phenomena that has already occurred (Punch and Oncaea, 2014; Mertler, 2019). Sabana (2014) states that this strategy is recommendable because the approach researchers to gather quantitative data that can be analyzed quantitatively using inferential analysis. The researcher prefers this design because it facilitates collecting of reliable information while demonstrating the real traits of celebrity endorsement and buying intentions among consumers in Western Kenya.

Target Population

This is units sets, entirely, for which research data are to be utilized for conclusions; it identifies the units for which study discoveries are expected to generalize (Mertler, 2019). This study targeted population is 57,715 students of the public universities and University colleges in Western Kenya, this include: Maseno University, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, as well as Kibabii University. To determine the target population size, the study adopted the student population from the various university websites.

Table 1: Study Target Population

University/ College	Target Population	% Population
Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology.	25,000	43%
Kibabii University	11,715	20%
Maseno University	21,000	37%
Total	57,715	100%

Source: Respective University Websites for 2020

The study involved three Ariel product merchandisers from each of three towns (Kakamega town, Bungoma town and Maseno town, where the respective universities are located), as key informants to provide key information on the celebrity endorsement and Ariel product consumer purchase intentions.

Sampling Procedure

According to Ustafa (2010), sampling is about obtaining a desired sample of items out of a study population. For this study, more than one sampling approach were used because of characteristics unique to the targeted population. For instance, in this research the population size to be sampled is large and it varied substantially in its composition. And therefore, sample procedures were utilized in this study included: stratified simple random sampling and purposive sampling (Kothari, 2010). Numerous experts have recognized that stratified sampling is suitable when dealing with non-uniform populations (Vaus, 2001).

The study applied stratified simple random sampling to sample respondents from the students of the three selected public Universities in Western Kenya (Maseno University, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, as well as Kibabii University). Purposive sampling was used to obtain the four Ariel product merchandisers who will be key informants in giving information on celebrity endorsement and the Ariel product purchase intention among consumers in Western Kenya.

Sample Size

This research utilized the following formula to establish the study sample size:

Equation 1: Formula for Determination of Sample Size (Yamane, 1967);

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

- n = the sample size
- N = the population size
- e^2 = desired level of statistical significance (0.05)

Therefore;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} = \frac{57,715}{1 + 57,715(0.05)^2} = 397.2468 \approx 397$$

Thus, the study adopted a sample of 397 respondents that was a representative of the consumer residents of the three universities in Western Kenya.

To determine the sample size of each i^{th} town, the study used proportionate stratified random sampling. A proportion of the sample size was calculated to establish the respondents in each stratum (i^{th} town) to be examined as follows:

$$Proportion = \frac{Sample}{Population} = \frac{397}{57,715} = 0.00687862773975569$$

Therefore, the i^{th} town sample size was as calculated in table 3.2 below:

Table 2: Study Population and Sample Sizes

City/Town	Population Size	Proportion
MMUST	25,000	0.0068786
Kibabii University	11,715	0.0068786
Maseno University	21,000	0.0068786
Total	57,715	

Source: Respective University Websites

Data Collection Instruments

Well-designed structured questionnaires was employed to get information from the study respondents who are part of the student population in three selected public Universities in Western Kenya (Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Maseno University and Kibabii University). Interview schedule was employed to gather information from key informants, who are the Ariel product merchandisers in the major towns where the Universities are located; Kakamega town, Bungoma town and Luanda town). This was through purposive sampling to ensure the merchandiser's were serving a huge student population in the area, and are indeed merchandisers of the Ariel detergent.

Reliability of the Research Instruments.

The internal consistency of the questionnaire scale internal consistency was assessed for reliability; this will be measured and calculated using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated using the following formula.(Gill et al, 2020)

Here N is equal to the number of items, \bar{c} is the average inter-item co variance among the items and \bar{v} equals the average variance. Alpha coefficient of between 0.6 and 0.9 was considered sufficient for yielding consistent results for the study. To enhance reliability of results, the responses have to be consistent. The greater the consistency, the more dependable the data would be.

Validity of Research Instruments

The study ensured that both construct and content validity are done so as to ascertain validity of the study tools. Experts in the field of celebrity endorsement and purchase intention, and University supervisors was involved in intensive analysis of both the structured questionnaire and the interview schedule and assessed their relevance and appropriateness to the study. The content validity targets adequate and sufficient coverage of the content of interest by the study items (Oluwatayo, 2012).

For this study, construct validity was used to measure if items that are used to measure a particular construct of the study actually measure the same thing. For the purpose of construct validity, the study questionnaire had several sections; this ensured that each segment analyzed data for a specific objective while also ensuring that it was clearly related to the study's conceptual framework. Construct validity was tested using principal component analysis, in specific, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test of sampling adequacy. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test was used to measure the adequacy of the sample size of items utilized in measurement of a certain construct. The KMO was calculated using the following formulae (Engelland et al, 2016).

$$KMO_j = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j} r_{ij}^2}{\sum_{i \neq j} r_{ij}^2 + \sum_{i \neq j} u_{ij}^2}$$

where the correlation matrix is $R = [rij]$ and the partial co variance matrix is $U = [uij]$. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was employed in the analysis to see if sampled respondents have similar variances. Factor loading will be determined to measure if the items actually measure the same thing.

Data Collection

With the help of six research assistants, the researcher disseminated the research instrument. A period of one week was given to the respondents in collecting data by filling out questionnaires. The study adopted this approach since the approach minimized on the costs and time involved during fieldwork. The questionnaire approach of data collection enabled the researcher to gather adequate information that is not biased; thus, answers were in respondents' own thinking. The questionnaire method of data collecting also provided enough time for research participants to provide thoughtful responses. This also allows the researcher to employ large representative samples, making the results more accurate. The researcher administer questionnaires to respondents who was consumers Ariel product among the students of the selected public universities in Western Kenya (Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Kibabii University, and Maseno University). The Interview schedules was administered to key informants (three Ariel product merchandisers).

Ethical Considerations

In this study ethics was considered accordingly as by Breweton *et al.* (2001). The researcher obtained a study permit from NACOSTI before proceeding to data collection from the field. The researcher further

sought the consent and attention of interviewee (key informants for the study) before conducting any interview and explain to them the aim of the interview and the privacy expected of the data to be given. There was appropriate acknowledgement of any other scholars' research work and materials used through proper citation of the sources of the reference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Response Rate

The researcher delivered 397 questionnaires at random to study participants who are students at three different public universities in Western Kenya (Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Kibabii University, and Maseno University). Fortunately, 370 of 397 questionnaires were duly filled and given back. This results in a response rate of 93 percent (see table 4.1), which coincides with Zikmund's (2010) argument that a response rate of more than 50.0 percent is required for generalization of the findings' conclusions.

Table 3: Response Rate

City/Town	Sample size	Participants	Return Rate (%)
MMUST	172	120	94%
Kibabii University	81	60	87%
Maseno University	144	190	95%
Total	397	370	93%

For the interviews, the study selected one Ariel merchant from each of the three regions of the selected Universities (Kakamega town near MMUST, Bungoma town near Kibabii University, and Luanda town near Maseno University). All the three merchants accepted and were accessible for the interview to provide key information on the Ariel detergent celebrity endorsement and its influence on the consumer purchase intentions.

Validity and Reliability tests

A pilot study test was carried out at Alupe University College, Busia County ,Kenya where 20 different respondents were involved. The purpose of this pilot study was to assess the validity and reliability of the research tools that would be used in the main study. For validity, both content and construct validity were checked while for reliability, the 5-point Likert scale was tested if it was reliable enough where coefficient alpha was used to determine if the proposed threshold of 0.7 for adequate reliable research instrument was attained. The findings were as detailed in the following subsections.

Table 4. Factor Analysis for Multiple Celebrity Endorsement Based on a Principal Components’ Analysis with Varimax Rotation for 4 items.

Statement	Factor Loading	Communalities	Decision
The presence of more than one celebrity in an advertisement makes it persuasive.	.643	.962	Retained
The presence of more than one celebrity in an advertisement makes it convincing.	.720	.538	Retained
More than one celebrity in a single advertisement makes it appealing	.855	.792	Retained
More than one celebrity in a single advertisement makes it dynamic.	.831	.723	Retained

The Table shows that the communalities for all four items in the Multiple Celebrity Endorsement Construct were all greater than 0.3 (Costello & Osborne, 2008), exhibiting that the items shared a similar variance.

Reliability Analysis

To investigate the reliability of the 5-point Likert scale employed in the questionnaire to measure the research components (variables), a reliability test was performed. To accomplish this, a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.7 was chosen as the minimal criterion for determining the adequacy of the research scale's reliability (Kendell & Jablensky, 2003).The reliability test results are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 5: Reliability Test Results

Variables (Constructs)	Number of items	Cronbach Alpha
Consumer Purchase Intentions	6	0.822
Gender of Celebrity	5	0.710
Credibility of Celebrity	10	0.975
Attractiveness of the Celebrity	6	0.853
Multiple Celebrity Endorsement	4	0.788
Overall	31	0.898

Table 5 obviously exhibits that Cronbach alpha coefficients for all variables were more than the minimal requirement of 0.7. (Kendell, 2003); Consumer Purchase Intentions = 0.822, Gender of Celebrity = 0.710, Credibility of Celebrity = 0.975, Attractiveness of the Celebrity = 0.853 and Multiple Celebrity Endorsement = 0.788. The total Alpha coefficient was 0.898, which was above the 0.7 minimal criteria. As a result, our study indicated that the 5-point scale of the items utilized to measure the study constructs was suitable as well as reliable for further investigation.

Demographic Characteristics

Respondent demographic information comprised the respondent's university, gender, age, and greatest educational level obtained. The results were as predicted in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

According to figure 4.1, 65 percent of the respondents were male, while 35 percent were female; this indicates that the study guaranteed gender parity throughout the data gathering procedure. It is also apparent that the bulk of respondents (44 percent) were between the ages of 26 and 35, as seen in figure 4.1. While 28 % were between the ages of 36 and 45, 17 percent were under the age of 25, and 11 % were 46 and above, indicating that the most of respondents were mature enough to provide trustworthy information for this study. Furthermore, 59 % had a University first degree and % had reached the

Diploma level of education, indicating that the most of respondents were suitably literate enough to grasp the researcher's questions posed in the field. As a result, the information provided may be depended on for this study.

Descriptive Statistics

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the descriptive statistics of the study's dependent variable (consumer purchase intentions) as well as the independent factors (Multiple Celebrity Endorsement).

Multiple Celebrity Endorsement.

The study sought to assess the descriptive statistics of multiple celebrity endorsement plus its influence on the purchase intention among public university students in Western Kenya. This would assist in determining the level of satisfaction among the public

university students in Western Kenya on multiple celebrity endorsement and how it would influence the Ariel detergent intentions to purchase. Table 4.13 exhibits the findings.

Table 6: Descriptive Analysis for Multiple Celebrity Endorsement. Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1, Disagree (D) = 2, Undecided (U) = 3, Agree (A) = 4, Strongly Agree (SA) = 5.

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
The presence of more than one celebrity in an advertisement makes it persuasive.	18 5%	22 6%	127 34%	149 40%	54 15%
The presence of more than one celebrity in an advertisement makes it convincing.	18 5%	25 7%	126 34%	160 43%	41 11%
More than one celebrity in a single advertisement makes it appealing	94 25%	22 6%	119 32%	55 15%	80 22%
More than one celebrity in a single advertisement makes it dynamic.	14 4%	91 25%	38 10%	69 19%	158 43%
Average Level of Multiple Celebrity Endorsement	Mean(%Mean) 3.4677 (69%)	Std. Dev. 0.78721	Std. Error of mean 0.04092	Minimum 2.00	Maximum 5.00

The findings of table shows that majority of the respondents, 40% agreed that the presence of more than one celebrity in an advertisement makes it persuasive to buy the product. Similarly, majority of the respondents, 43% agreed that presence of more than one celebrity in an advertisement makes it convincing for the customer to buy the Ariel detergent. Also, most of the respondents, 43% strongly agreed that more than one celebrity in a single advertisement makes it dynamic and thus attracting more customers to buy the product. However, most of the respondents, 32% were uncertain if having more than one celebrity in a single advertisement makes it appealing. Overall, the average level of multiple celebrity endorsement was at 69% (mean= 3.4677, Std. dev. = 0.78721) rated moderate signifying that most of the selected public university studies in Western Kenya were moderately satisfied in the multiple celebrity endorsement in the advertisement of the Ariel detergent in Western

Kenya. The research therefore purposed to evaluate the impact of multiple celebrity endorsement on the Consumer’s Purchase Intentions among the public university students in Western Kenya.

Correlation Analysis

The study utilized correlation analysis, in specific Pearson moment correlation (r) to evaluate the strength as well as direction of the relationship among celebrity endorsement (Multiple Celebrity Endorsement) and Consumer Purchase Intention among public university students in Western, Kenya. According to (Gravetter *et. al*, 2000), the correlation coefficient r ranges from +1 to -1; a coefficient, $|r| \leq 0.1$ indicating an insignificant relationship, $0.1 \leq |r| < 0.3$ indicates a weak association, $0.3 \leq |r| < 0.5$ indicates a moderate association, and $|r| \geq 0.5$ implies a strong association.

Table 7: Correlation Matrix

	Consumer Purchase Intentions	Gender of Celebrity	Credibility of the Celebrity	Attractiveness of Celebrity	Multiple Celebrity Endorsement
Multiple Celebrity Endorsement	Pearson Correlation .735**	.541**	.776**	.696**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	370	370	370	370

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

The table shows that there was strong positive correlation between Consumer Purchase Intentions as well as celebrity endorsement variables (Multiple Celebrity Endorsement) among public university students in Western, Kenya as indicated by; $r = 0.735$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$ respectively).

Linear Regression Analysis

The study utilized simple linear regression analysis for the study hypothesis testing, that is examining the significance of the casual and effect relationship between celebrity endorsement (Multiple Celebrity

Endorsement) and Consumer Purchase Intention among public university students in Western, Kenya. Multiple linear regression was utilized in determination of the partial influence of independent variables to the dependent variable and thus able to strength of the celebrity endorsements (Multiple Celebrity Endorsement) in influencing Consumer Purchase Intention among public university students in Western, Kenya.

Simple Linear Regression between Multiple Celebrity Endorsement and Consumer Purchase Intentions

The study’s fourth objective of the study was to determine the effect of multiple celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intention of

public university students in Western Kenya. The following hypothesis was tested by the researcher : *Multiple Celebrity Endorsement has no significant influence on the consumer purchase intention of public university students.*

Table 8: Linear Regression Analysis for the Multiple Celebrity Endorsement and Consumer Purchase Intentions

Model Summary						
Model	r	r-square	Adjusted r-square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.735 ^a	.540	.539	.48043		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Multiple Celebrity Endorsement						
b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Intentions						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
1	Regression	99.771	1	99.771	432.268	.000 ^b
	Residual	84.937	368	.231		
	Total	184.708	369			
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Intentions						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Multiple Celebrity Endorsement						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value
			Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.145	.113		10.140	.000
	Multiple Celebrity Endorsement	.661	.032	.735	20.791	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Intentions						

The F (1, 368) = 432.268, p-value = 0.000 <0.05 ANOVA test findings from table 4.20 implies that the Simple Linear Regression model was an excellent match to our data set. The model (Multiple Celebrity Endorsement) managed to clarify 54% of the variation in consumer purchase intention of public university students Western, Kenya as indicated by the r-square = 0.540 as shown in table 4.6’s model summary. The unstandardized beta coefficient was significant, = 0.661, p-value = 0.000 < 0.05 as depicted by the regression coefficient outcomes; therefore, the study rejected the null hypothesis and conclude that Multiple Celebrity Endorsement has a statistically significant positive influence on the consumer purchase intention of public university students Western, Kenya.

Multiple celebrity endorsement had a positive standardized beta coefficient = 0.735 as exhibited in table 4.6’s coefficients outcomes; this uncovers that a unit increment in the Multiple Celebrity Endorsement would probably cause an improvement in the Consumer Purchase Intentions of University Students in Western Kenya by 73.5%. To predict the consumer purchase intention of public university students Western, Kenya when provided the multiple celebrity endorsement level.

The following model is suggested by the study; Consumer Purchase Intentions = 0.991 + 0.569 Multiple Celebrity Endorsement. These findings were supported by key informants who agreed that endorsement of the Ariel detergent by multiple

celebrities had a significant effect on the Ariel detergent consumer purchase intentions as indicated by 100% response in support as shown in figure 4.14 below.

Figure: Multiple celebrity endorsement and its influence on customer purchase intentions

The explanation given by the key informants suggested that sales of Ariel detergent in the market also depends on the commodity endorsement by multiple celebrities as indicated in the quote below:

.... when more than one celebrities are used to market any product including the Ariel detergent at the same time, the customers’ confidence in the product is likely to increase since it will be like people are for the product.

The study findings complement the findings by Hsu and McDonald (2002) in a study on multiple endorsements for consumer behavior where it was

found that brand ambassadors complement one another even with their diversities in a multiple endorsement strategy. This ensures that the product or brand promoted acquires a wider view of transferred meanings. However, even in the place of their similarities, the similarities work as emphasis. Reebok (2005) launched its embarked on a global multifaceted campaign dubbed (I am what I am). It advocated for youngsters to celebrate their icons such as the singers and sports persons. The result of this initiative has been leveraged by several firms that have engaged these icons on the promotional platforms. Some managers however believe that an icon would influence more sales through brand image than any other means; they are seen to have very strong personalities that easily change perceptions of people.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

Multiple Celebrity Endorsement and its Influence on the Consumer Purchase Intentions

According to the study findings, the existence of more than one celebrity in an advertising makes it more appealing to target customers to buy the product being advertised. This makes it convincing, dynamic and thus attracting more customers to buy the advertised product. However, the study revealed that having multiple celebrities endorsing a particular product does not necessarily mean that the product would be appealing in the eyes of the target customers. It was also revealed that multiple celebrity endorsement was not certain in persuading the target customers to buying a certain customer.

Conclusion

The study concluded that multiple celebrity endorsement had a statistically significant strong positive influence on the customer purchase intentions. That existence of more than one celebrity in an advertisement makes it appealing to target customers to buy the product being advertised; it makes it convincing, dynamic and thus attracting more customers to buy the advertised product.

In general, the study concludes that the four celebrity endorsement factors (gender of celebrity, credibility and attractiveness of the celebrity, as well as multiple celebrity endorsement) had significant influence on the customer purchase intentions. However, besides the four factors, there are other factors not covered in this study that significantly influences the customer purchase intentions.

Recommendations

The study recommends that brands and marketers ought to consider the credibility of a celebrity before engaging them to endorse their products. That their behaviour, trust and reliability are key in determining whether or not customers watching an advert

promoted by the celebrity would be influenced to buy the product.

Brands that wish to use celebrities to market their products should consider using the approach of multiple endorsers since it is indeed convincing, dynamic and thus influencing more customers to buy the advertised product.

REFERENCES

- [1] Akinyi, R.J. (2017). *The influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer's purchasing decisions of fast-moving consumer goods among low and middle social class in Nairobi County, Kenya*. (Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya).
- [2] Baker, M. J., & Churchill Jr, G. A. (1977). The impact of physically attractive models on advertising evaluations. *Journal of Marketing research*, 14(4), 538-555.
- [3] Breweton, P. & Millward, L. 2001. *Organizational Research Methods*, London, SAGE.
- [4] Caballero, M. J., Lumpkin, J. R., & Madden, C. S. (1989). Using physical attractiveness as an advertising tool: An empirical test of the attraction phenomenon. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 29(4), 16-22.
- [5] Clow, K. E., James, K. E., Kranenburg, K. E., & Berry, C. T. (2006). The relationship of the visual element of an advertisement to service quality expectations and source credibility. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 20(6), 404-411.
- [6] Erdogan, B. Z. (1999). Celebrity endorsement: a literature review. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15(4), 291-314.
- [7] Erdogan, B. Z., Baker, M. J., & Tagg, S. (2001). Selecting celebrity endorsers: the practitioner's perspective. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 41(3), 39 - 49.
- [8] Gill, J., Johnson, P. & Clark, M. 2010. *Research Methods for Managers*, SAGE Publications.
- [9] Goldsmith, R. E., Lafferty, B. A., & Newell, S. J. (2000). The impact of corporate credibility and celebrity credibility on consumer reaction to advertisements and brands. *Journal of advertising*, 29(3), 435-4.
- [10] Hsu, C.K., & McDonald, D. (2002). An examination on multiple celebrity endorsers in advertising. *Journal of Product and Brand Management*, 11(1), 19-29.
- [10] Kelman, H. (1961). Processes of opinion change. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 33, 57-78.
- [11] Kendall, E. L., & Sproles, G. B. (1986). Learning Styles among Secondary Vocational Home Economics Students: A Factor Analytic Test of Experiential Learning Theory. *Journal of Vocational Education Research*, 11(3), 1-15.
- [12] Kothari C.R., (2010), *Research Methodology: Methods and Technique*, New Delhi: New Age International Publishers, p. 31

- [13] McCracken, G. (1989). Who is the celebrity endorser? Cultural foundations of the endorsement process. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 16(3), 310–321.
- [14] Mertler, C. A. (2019). Introduction to Educational Research. 2nd Ed. Sage publications. New Delhi
- [15] Milosavljevic, M., & Cerf, M. (2008). First attention then intention: Insights from computational neuroscience of vision. *International Journal of Advertising*, 27(3), 381-398.
- [16] Mugenda, A. & Mugenda, O. (2006) *Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. (2nd Ed.). Nairobi: ACTS.
- [17] Mugenda, O. M., & Mugenda, A. G. (2003). *Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Nairobi: African Centre for Technology Studies.
- [18] Mwikya, K. M. (2013). *Relational factors influencing timely service delivery at Kenya Airways* (Unpublished Research Project Report, University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya).
- [19] Njuguna, S., & Otieno, H. (2015) *Influence of Celebrity Endorsements on Young Consumers: Brand Recall Behaviour in Kenya, A Case Study of Nairobi County*. Nairobi: Strathmore University
- [20] Nzomo V. (2013). Unilever [Omo] vs Procter & Gamble [Ariel]: Regulation of Advertising under Kenya's Competition and Intellectual Property Laws.
- [21] Oluwatayo, J. 2012. Validity and reliability issues in educational research. *Journal of Educational and Social Research* 2, 391-400
- [22] Punch, K.F., & Oancea, A. (2014). Introduction to Research Methods in Education. 2^{ne} Ed. Sage Publications. New Delhi.
- [23] Sabana, B. M. (2014). Entrepreneur financial literacy, financial access, transaction costs and performance of micro enterprises in Nairobi City County, Kenya. *An unpublished PHD project University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya*.
- [24] Schiffman, L. G., Kanuk, L. L., & Hansen, H. (2008). *Consumer behaviour: A European outlook*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- [25] Schiffman, L.G. & Kanuk, L.L. (2010). *Consumer Behavior*. (10th ed.). Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [26] Schiffman, L.G., Kanuk, L.L., & Hansen, H. (2012). *Consumer Behaviour: A European Outlook*. (2nd ed.). Essex: Pearson Education.
- [27] Singer, B. D. (1983). The case for using 'real people in advertising. *Business Quarterly*, 48(4), 32-37.
- [28] Ustafa A., (2010), *Research Methodology*, Delhi: A.I.T.B.S Publishers, p. 86,87
- [29] Vaus David de. (2001), *Research Design in Social Research*, New Delhi: Sage Publication, p.16
- [30] Zhao, R., Yang, M., Liu, J., Yang, L., Bao, Z., & Ren, X. (2020). University Students' Purchase Intention and Willingness to Pay for Carbon-Labeled Food Products: A Purchase Decision-Making Experiment. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(19), 7026.